
Research

Kenya's Economic Development since 2000: The Role of China's Economic Engagement

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Abstract: Over the past two decades, China-Africa economic relations have developed considerably since the establishment of the first forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC) in 2000. Both need each other in terms of trade whilst for Kenya Chinese economic development assistance comes without any conditions. Moreover, China's Belt and Road (BRI) has been billed as the single most significant undertaking by the country on the international stage. China's extensive economic engagement in Kenya, especially through its flagship BRI projects, raises important questions with respect to its contribution to Kenyan economic development. This article therefore analyses the economic development implications for Kenya of China's economic engagement, over the last two decades, with a specific focus upon infrastructural investment as the main instrument of Kenyan economic development. Infrastructure development theory is used in this paper, since it is a theory of long-run development based on public infrastructure as the engine of growth. Therefore, this paper evaluates the development implications for Kenya of its deepening economic engagement with China through a case study of multiple infrastructure projects by Chinese companies to improve Kenya's transport system such as the Standard Gauge Railway (SGR). The principal conclusions of this article emphasize the importance of China's infrastructure investment as one of the major factors in Kenya's economic development since 2000, despite negative public perceptions and critiques. But, this paper also identifies policy lessons for other countries in East Africa in terms of the Chinese economic development model and the vital importance of infrastructural investment for national economic development.

Keywords: Kenyan economic development, China-Africa economic relations, infrastructural development, FOCAC, BRI, Kenya's Vision 2030

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Introduction

“Faced with the various risks and challenges, it is more important for emerging markets and developing countries to strengthen solidarity and cooperation”¹ noted the State Councillor and Chinese Foreign Minister Wang Yi during the Video Dialogue of between BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) Foreign Ministers, Emerging Markets and Developing Countries in Beijing in May 19, 2022. Some two decades earlier, in 2000, the Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC) was established initiating a new chapter in Sino-African cooperation to “Deepen the Sino-African partnership and promote sustainable development to build a Sino-African shared community in the new era”² (with 53 African members states) is a platform promoting China-Africa economic relations. Since its inception in 2000, FOCAC has facilitated collective dialogue and practical economic cooperation between China and Africa.³ Kenya, given it has the largest economy in East Africa, is a major player in and a significant beneficiary of Chinese development assistance. Accordingly this article examines China’s economic engagement in Kenya and its contribution to Kenyan economic development.

China’s economic engagement in East Africa is marked by deepening trade, investment, and financial relationships, which benefits both parties while respecting each other’s national policies. Certainly, the key to Africa’s success is trade, although, its economic relationship with China also extends to infrastructure investment and development aid. But, to facilitate trade, one needs infrastructure which is lacking in East African countries and in Africa in general. Empirical research has shown that infrastructure has positive effects on both trade and economic growth in Africa⁴. This is one of the reasons for African economic engagement with China’s Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), which has infrastructure construction as its main objective⁵.

This article analyses the contributions of Chinese economic engagement to Kenyan economic development through infrastructural investment contrasts with much of the existing literature on China’s economic engagement in Africa which tends to concern itself with analyzing the possible rationales and motivations for China’s engagement in this region. Thus, a distinctive contribution of this paper is its examination of the development consequences for Kenya, both in respect of indicators of economic development and the government’s economic development strategy (Kenya Vision 2030), of China’s deepening economic engagement since 2000.

Kenya’s Vision 2030 represents the country’s latest development strategy, which covers the period 2008-2030. It aims to transform Kenya into a newly industrializing, “middle-income country providing a high quality life to all its

¹ Yi Wang, “Speech about Dialogue of Foreign Ministers between BRICS and Emerging Markets and Developing Countries”, Beijing, May 19, 2022. Published online by Ministry of Foreign Affairs of People’s Republic of China (2022-05-20). Available at https://www.fmprc.gov.cn/mfa_eng/top-ics_665678/kjgzbdffyq/202205/t20220520_10690435.html

² “Forum on China-Africa Cooperation Dakar Action Plan (2022-2024)”, Dakar, Senegal, from November 29th to 30th 2021, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of People’s Republic of China. 2021. (The 8th Ministerial Conference of FOCAC) Available at https://www.fmprc.gov.cn/mfa_eng/wjdt_665385/2649_665393/202112/t20211202_10461183.html

³ UNDP, “FOCAC: In Perspective”, *Issue Brief, No. 14, December 2015*, (September 21, 2016): 1-2.

⁴ Rodgers Mukwaya, and Andrew Mold, « Modeling the economic impact of the China Belt and Road Initiative on East Africa », *GTAP 21st Annual Conference on Global Economic Analysis*, (2018): p. 2.

⁵ Full text of President Xi’s speech at opening of Belt and Road forum. Chinese President Xi Jinping delivers a keynote speech at the opening ceremony of the Belt and Road Forum (BRF) for International Cooperation in Beijing, capital of China, May 14, 2017. (Xinhua/Wang Ye). Available at http://www.xinhuanet.com/english/2017-05/14/c_136282982.htm

citizens by the year 2030"⁶. In recent times China has played a significant role not just in supporting Kenya's economic development strategy but more generally as a successful model of national economic development such that the Kenyan case may have valuable policy lessons for other countries in the East African region and on the African continent itself.

Background

As noted Sino-Africa economic relations are not new. Contrary to popular perception, they can be traced to a few years after the establishment of the People's Republic of China in 1949.⁷ This initial period of cooperation lasted until roughly around 1978 when China introduced market-based economic reforms. During this period, China supported African countries in their struggle for independence from the colonial powers and provided economic assistance to newly independent African countries in opposition to colonialism and imperialism.⁸ This was very important for those African countries at that time due seeking national independence. Many African countries became independent during the 1960s and 1970s providing a great opportunity for countries such as China to engage with newly independent countries such as Kenya.

To go back in history, Kenya became independent from British colonization on June 1st, 1963. The People's Republic of China established diplomatic relations with the Republic of Kenya on the day of December 14, 1963. And since the establishment of diplomatic relations, aid projects and assistance, and bilateral trade increased greatly most especially in recent years. The economic relationship is reciprocal such that China exports much electronic equipment to Kenya whilst the latter exports primary products such as coffee and raw materials to China...⁹

Kenya was formerly one of Africa's strongest economies, with average annual growth of five per cent in the late 1980s, based on agriculture (notably tea and coffee production and horticulture) and tourism. Poor harvests and political uncertainty slowed growth in the early 1990s; a foreign exchange crisis resulting from the withholding of aid by donors between December 1991 and November 1993 brought low growth and high inflation (46 per cent in 1993). The country has been afflicted by recurring droughts over two decades. Consequently, while Kenya ranks among the leaders of the post-colonial effort to industrialize in Africa, its industrial development has not been equal to its recent growth or national objectives. Manufacturing, which is a key driver of overall growth in Kenya, has declined significantly over the last three decades.¹⁰

The extensive economic engagement of China in Africa today has very deep historical roots. Chinese economic engagement is not a new or temporary phenomenon in most parts of Africa.¹¹ Over the two past decades, China-Africa

⁶ Government of Republic of Kenya, "Kenya Vision 2030: The popular Version", Summary of Kenya's new long-term national planning strategy, officially known as Kenya Vision 2030, (2007): 1-26.

⁷ Jinyuan G, "China and Africa: the development of relations over many centuries", *African Affairs* 83(331), (1984): 241-250.

⁸ Kassaye, Gudeta Deyassa, "To what extent does China's aid in Africa affect traditional donors?", Department of Geography, Faculty of Social Sciences, Universitetet i Bergen, Bergen, Norway, *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy* Vol. 39 No. 5/6, (2019): 398.

⁹ Embassy of the People's Republic of China in the Republic of Kenya. Available at <http://ke.china-embassy.org/eng/sbgx/t169682.htm>

¹⁰ Githaiga N., "Kenya-China Trade in Manufactured Goods: A Competitive or Complementary Relationship?", *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 9, (2021): 96-117.

¹¹ Deborah Brautigam, "China in Africa: Seven myths", *Elcano Newsletter Issue 74, Real Instituto Elcano*. (2011): p.2.

relations have developed considerably. In 2000, since its inception, FOCAC has fostered strategic collaboration, resulting in a sharp increase in diplomatic and economic cooperation initiatives. Moreover, it meets every three years in order to agree new development initiatives and for member states to renew their commitment to strategic collaboration.

This article therefore analyzes economic cooperation between China and Kenya from 2000 which is the year in which the first official Forum on China-Africa Cooperation was held. Since then China's economic relations with its African partners, particularly with Kenya have rapidly developed and radically deepened. Moreover, since 2000, several African economies, including Kenya, have performed as well as or better than China because they have benefited from the boom in commodity prices associated with growing Chinese demand.

Literature review

In general, all countries in East Africa are geopolitically important to China as well as to other international actors, not least as an important shipping route connecting the Indian Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea¹². Demissie and Brautigam find that it is not a coincidence that three of four China-Africa production capacity cooperation countries are actually based in East Africa¹³.

Moreover, when it comes to Chinese economic engagement in Africa, the discourse and rhetoric are often at odds with what facts and evidence tell us.¹⁴ The number of press articles and academic works devoted to the Chinese presence in Africa has literally exploded in the last twenty years due to the rapid increase of Chinese investments in the East African area such as Kenya, Tanzania, and Ethiopia. Academic opinions differ; some scholars such as David Pilling¹⁵ find China's economic engagement in Africa opportunistic. While others such as Ken Kamoche, Saileshsingh Gunessee, and Nana K. Kufuor argue that Chinese economic engagement has significant positive implications for Africa's economic fortunes.¹⁶ Soule also argues that, China's growing economic engagement with Africa has had a positive, albeit uneven, effect on Africa's economic growth, economic diversification, job creation, infrastructure and connectivity¹⁷.

Indeed, China's presence in the construction of mega infrastructure projects in Kenya has generated security concerns arising from local frustrations over lack of job opportunities for Kenyans.¹⁸ However, since China's

¹² Alexander, Demissie, « Special Economic Zones : Integrating African Countries in China's Belt and Road Initiative », in *Rethinking the Silk Road*, ed. M. Mayer, (University of Cologne, Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn, Bonn, Germany, 2018), 78.

¹³ Ibidem. p. 70.

¹⁴ Deborah Brautigam, "China in Africa: Seven myths", *Elcano Newsletter Issue 74, Real Instituto Elcano*, (2011): 1-7.

¹⁵ David Pilling, "Chinese investment in Africa: Beijing's testing ground", *Financial Times*, (2017)

¹⁶ Ken Kamoche, Saileshsingh Gunessee & Nana K. Kufuor, "The Africa-China engagement: *Contemporary developments and directions for future research*", *Africa Journal of Management*, (2021): 1.

¹⁷ Soule Folashade, and Selormey Edem E., « What Africans really think about China's role in Africa », *Quartz Africa Mindspace*, (2020).

¹⁸ Oscar M. Otele, "China-Kenya Relations: Economic benefits set against regional risks", in *Beyond blocs: Global views on China and US-China relations*, ed. Jacob Gunter and Helena Legarda (Mercator Institute for China Studies (MERICS), No. 11, 2022), 54-60.

involvement in the country, Kenya has been able to enjoy strong protection from the insecurity in the region as China sought to secure its maritime safety from pirates along the major sea lanes connecting East Africa to Chinese ports.

As with any long and complex relationship, the Africa-China economic engagement includes both benefits and challenges. According to African government officials, China's contribution to infrastructure in Africa comes with several benefits: cost effectiveness, administrative efficiency, and speedy delivery without compromising quality¹⁹. Kenya, along with Ethiopia, is one of the African countries most involved in the BRI. Several memoranda of understanding and agreements across a wide range of sectors have been signed between Kenya and China in recent years. These have included agreements to strengthen Chinese tourism in Kenya (2014), to increase Kenyan agricultural exports to the Chinese market and to strengthen innovation (2018).²⁰

Moreover, Chinese investment in Kenya has shown some other positive aspects. As noted in a World Bank report²¹, Chinese businesses in Kenya employ, on average, 360 local employees, far higher than the average 147 local employees employed in other foreign-invested enterprises in Kenya.

However, although the Kenyan government and the public seems to have a positive perception of Chinese economic engagement in the country, some discord has emerged in recent past. Pilling²² notes the potential for a debt threat to Africa posed by China because African governments are so indebted to China that they are pledging their political and economic independence. Despite this, he nevertheless concludes that, from an African perspective, while there are many risks, the partnership with China brings tangible benefits in terms of development finance and infrastructure. For example, Kenya benefits from Chinese aid estimated at several billion dollars - as well as their expertise in engineering to improve its infrastructure.²³

Research Methodology

This paper uses a single case study approach focused on Kenya since it plays an indispensable role in the East African region due to its infrastructure development which has positive effects on growth and trade in East Africa and in Africa in general.²⁴ A case study approach enables an in-depth, detailed examination of a particular case (or cases) within a real-world context. In general terms, the case study analyzes a defined problem consisting in a real situation and uses real information as methodological tool.²⁵ This paper will also adopt a mixed method approach to the case study using quantitative and qualitative methods.

Quantitative data is essential to identify and evaluate development trends and economic patterns in multiple sectors such as trade, investment, and infrastructure. While the qualitative method uses academic, media sources,

¹⁹ Irene Yuan Sun, Kartik Jayaram, and Omid Kassiri. « Dance of the Lions and the Dragons: How are Africa and China engaging, and how will the partnership evolve? », *McKinsey & Company*. (June 2017).

²⁰ Sebastien Goulard, "Obstacles to the BRI in Kenya", *One Belt One Road Europe (OBOReurope)*, last modified July 7, 2020. <https://www.oboreurope.com/en/obstacles-bri-kenya/>

²¹ "Informal Enterprises in Kenya", *World Bank Group*, Jan. 2016, available at <http://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/262361468914023771/pdf/106986-WP-P151793-PUBLIC-Box.pdf>

²² David Pilling, « Que cherche la Chine en investissant autant en Afrique ? », *Economie Jeune Afrique*, (2021), Published on 13-07-2017.

²³ Ibidem

²⁴ Soule Folashade, and Edem E. Selormey, « What Africans really think about China's role in Africa », *Quartz Africa Mindspace*, (2020): 2.

²⁵ "Case Studies and Comparative Analysis", *E - International Relations*, last modified August 18 2021, Available at <https://www.e-ir.info/2021/08/18/case-studies-and-comparative-analysis/>

archives, official government and international sources that provide descriptions and analysis of policy initiatives, decisions and bilateral partnerships.²⁶

Infrastructure development theory is a theory of long-run development based on public infrastructure as the engine of growth.²⁷ Infrastructure is essential to the production and distribution of industrial goods, commodities and health services such as road, railway, hospital.... As result of network effects, the degree of efficiency of infrastructure is nonlinearly related to the stock of public capital itself. Provided that governance is adequate enough to ensure a sufficient degree of efficiency of public investment, an increase in the share of spending on infrastructure may facilitate the shift from low growth equilibrium, characterized by low productivity and low savings, to a high growth steady state.²⁸ This theory hypothesizes that expanding infrastructure, through projects like BRI, not only creates jobs but long-term economic development. As Agénor states: “lack of infrastructure continues to be a key obstacle to growth and development in many low-income countries”²⁹, especially in Africa. So, according to this theory, infrastructure has a critical role in creating the conditions for national economic development.

Furthermore, according to Mashkoor, the economic development is the product of three interconnected factors: infrastructure development; trade development; and most importantly human development (See Figure 1).³⁰

Fig. 1: Hierarchy of Economic development, created by Aasim Mashkoor, in Theory of Economic Development (Pyramids of Development)³¹

Mashkoor reminds us of the critical importance of infrastructure for national economic development which is recognized explicitly in Kenya’s ambitious Vision 2030 development strategy.

²⁶ « China pledges to enhance bilateral cooperation with Kenya », Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC), 2019, Available at https://www.fmprc.gov.cn/zfhzlt2018/eng/zfgx_4/jmhz/t1660827.htm

²⁷ Pierre-Richard Agénor, “A Theory of Infrastructure-Led Development”, *Journal of Economic Dynamics and control*, Vol. 34(5). (2010): 932-950.

²⁸ Pierre-Richard Agénor, “A Theory of Infrastructure-Led Development”, *Journal of Economic Dynamics and control*, Vol. 34(5). (2010): 932-950.

²⁹ Ibidem.

³⁰ Ahmed, Ovais and Aasim Mashkoor. “Theory of Economic Development (Pyramids of Development).” (2015).

³¹ Ibidem P. 3.

Overview of Kenya's economy

Rapid economic growth across Africa, and in Kenya particularly, has been attributed to a whole range of factors: better government finances and fiscal policies reflected in reduced debt and general government expenditures ratios; booming commodity exports, especially to China, although the region runs a trade deficit with the country; increased FDI; new discoveries of oil and other minerals; the increased role of telecoms; ease of doing business reforms; and increased investment in education as well as democratization of the continent.³² However, there is a tendency within the more orthodox development literature to overlook the significance of deepening Chinese economic engagement.

First, Kenya is the largest and the most advanced economy in East and Central Africa; with strong growth prospects supported by an emerging, urban middle class and an increasing appetite for high-value goods and services.³³ Kenya is ranked the sixth largest economy in Africa with a GDP of \$ 98.84 billion in 2020, according to official data from the World Bank³⁴ up from the ninth largest economy in Africa in 2013.³⁵ Kenya has the second largest population within the East African Community (EAC) at 43 million and is growing at a rate of 2.7 per cent per annum.³⁶ There is a rising trend towards urbanization, which is contributing to an increase in consumer demand for high value goods. This trend is fore casted to continue, with 50 per cent of the population expected to live in urban areas by 2050. So, Kenya was and still the most developed of the original three countries of the East African Community (Kenya, Uganda and the United Republic of Tanzania). As it stands today, Kenya is the dominant economy in the EAC up from the fourth in Sub-Saharan Africa in 2013 (SSA). It is the primary source of foreign direct investment (FDI) for some of the countries of the Community too. Thus, Kenya is also an important test case for evaluating the impact of China's economic engagement in that it has experienced significantly increased Chinese presence in key sectors of the economy.³⁷

Secondly, Kenya's recently concluded general elections in August 2022, have set the stage for the next stage of its development. For whilst has implemented significant political and economic reforms that have contributed to sustained economic growth, social development, and political stability gains over the past decade it nevertheless still confronts key development challenges including poverty, inequality, youth unemployment, transparency and accountability, climate change, continued weak private sector investment, and the vulnerability of the economy to internal and external shocks.

³² Mwangi S., Kimenyi Francis M., Mwege Njuguna, S. Ndung'u. "The African Lions: Kenya country case study." *University of Cape Town on "Understanding the African Lions: Growth Traps and Opportunities in Six Dominant African Economies"*, (May 2016): 2.

³³ World Bank. "The World Bank in Kenya: The World Bank's work in Kenya supports the government's Vision 2030 development strategy, which aims to accelerate sustainable growth, reduce inequality, and manage resource scarcity". *World Bank report* in March 2021. Available at <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/kenya/overview#1>

³⁴ Ibidem

³⁵ S. Mwangi, Francis Kimenyi, M. Mwege, and Njuguna S. Ndung'u, « The African Lions: Kenya country case study », (May 2016): 1.

³⁶ "East Africa's Largest Economy", Kenya Investment Authority (KenInvest), last updated January, 2023, <http://www.invest.go.ke/why-invest-in-kenya-2/east-africa-largest-economy/>

³⁷ Sammy Mwangi Waweru, « Who is Against Sino-African Relations? Evolving Perceptions on Chinese Engagement in Kenya », *Chinese Journal of International Review* Vol. 2, No. 22050011 (2020): 22.

Kenya is 8th amongst 15 African countries in terms of the distribution of Chinese aid and investment projects in Africa. It receives around 4.1% of FDI project and 3.4% of FDI flows from China between 2003 to 2014 (according to the Information from MOFCOM and Aid Data).³⁸

Fig. 2: The total of Chinese FDI Inflow in Africa 2001 -2018 accessed in FDI data between 2001 and 2012 is obtained from United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), FDI data after 2012 is obtained from China Africa Research Initiative at Johns Hopkins University.³⁹

China's growing economic engagement in Kenya followed from a very turbulent period during the 1990's and early 2000's in its relationship with the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and other international agencies. In August 2000, IMF support (suspended since 1997) was resumed when it agreed a three-year poverty reduction and growth loan, conditional on all senior officials, including the President, declaring their assets each year. Relations with aid donors were strained during the period 2001–02, and some disbursements were delayed; relations only improved after the change of government in December 2002. The new government of Kenya committed itself to structural adjustment, including the privatization of Kenya Commercial Bank, Telkom Kenya and Kenya Railways; enacted anti-corruption legislation; and concluded a poverty reduction and growth facility with the IMF. Commitments of support by other multilateral and bilateral donors and a new round of debt rescheduling then followed.⁴⁰

³⁸ Yu Zheng, "China's Aid and Investment in Africa: A Viable Solution to International Development?", *Fudan University*, (2016): p.2.

³⁹ Carla D. Jones, Hermann A. Ndofor, Mengge Li, "Chinese economic engagement in Africa: Implications for U.S. Policy", Foreign Policy Research Institute, (2022). Available at <https://www.fpri.org/article/2022/01/chinese-economic-engagement-in-africa/>

⁴⁰ Available at <https://www.commonwealthgovernance.org/countries/africa/kenya/economy/>

As figure 3 indicates, Kenya experienced very slow economic growth in 2000, but the economy recovered by the mid-2000s, when it grew by at least five per cent p.a. Subsequently the impact of both drought and global recession, it slowed sharply (growing by 1.5 per cent in 2008), recovering in 2009 (2.7 per cent) but increasing significantly in 2010–14, with growth of four to six per cent p.a.⁴¹. The subsequent section analyses the relationship between Kenya’s growth trends and the expansion of China’s economic engagement have played during these periods in relation to Kenyan economic development?

Fig. 3. GDP growth (annual %) – Kenya: 2000-2020. World Bank national accounts data, and OECD National Accounts data, 2023.

China’s economic engagement and Kenyan economic development

Before discussing China’s contribution to Kenyan economic development, it is essential to understand China’s position in the world market and more specifically in Africa. First, China is the second largest economy in the world and one of the leading exporters to African countries. In the past two decades, China has catapulted from being a relatively small investor in the continent to becoming Africa’s largest economic partner. China is among the top four partners for Africa across five dimensions: investments trade, infrastructure financing, and aid.

China’s financial flows to Africa are around 15 percent larger than official figures when nontraditional flows are included. China is also a large and fast-growing source of aid and the largest source of construction financing; these contributions have supported many of Africa’s most ambitious infrastructure developments in recent years.⁴² Moreover, since 2003, the annual flow of Chinese foreign direct investment (FDI) to Africa has risen significantly from a mere \$74.8 million in 2003 to \$5.4 billion in 2018.⁴³ That makes China Africa’s fourth largest investor, ahead of the United States since 2014.⁴⁴

⁴¹ World Bank national accounts data, and OECD National Accounts data files. 2022. Available at <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.KD.ZG?locations=KE&start=2000>

⁴² Irene Yuan Sun, Kartik Jayaram, and Omid Kassiri, *Dance of the lions and dragons: How are Africa and China engaging, and how will the partnership evolve?*, (McKinsey & Company. June 2017): 9.

⁴³ Yike, Fu. “The Quiet China-Africa Revolution: Chinese Investment While loans take the lion’s share of the focus; Chinese FDI in Africa has also been growing at a rapid clip”. *The Diplomat*. 2021.

⁴⁴ Ibidem.

Wu Peng, Chinese ambassador to Kenya, notes that China-Kenya relations are standing at a higher stage with new development opportunities⁴⁵. He added that in 2018, China's non-financial direct investment in Kenya doubled to 52 billion shillings⁴⁶ (about 520 million U.S. dollars). And according to the United Nations Comtrade Database, China tops the list of Kenya's major trading partners (import sources) in 2020, with a share of 22% (3.39 billion US\$).⁴⁷

Since 2000, China's trade with Africa (See fig. 4) has been growing at approximately 20 percent per year.

Fig. 4: China-Africa bilateral trade data overview 2002-2020 by UN Comtrade, January 2022, In China Africa Research Initiative at Johns Hopkins School of Advanced International Studies, 2023.

China's economic presence in Kenya has attracted some criticism from the Former South African President Thabo Mbeki.⁴⁸ Other criticism has been that infrastructure aid is, in fact tied to the employment of Chinese companies and the use of Chinese sourced materials⁴⁹ rather than domestic companies and supplies which would benefit the domestic economy and thus Kenya's economic development. Not with standing these critical reactions, Chinese economic engagement in Kenya still has popular support from government, general citizenry and among those classes of Kenyans who have benefited from it.⁵⁰

However, the current attitudes of Kenyans toward China remain largely unknown. Surveys conducted by Kenyan scholars and institutions reveal interesting results about Kenyans' attitudes to China and the Chinese. As Omolo, Jairo and Wanja found "African states do not have a common ground that they can use as a bargaining chip to their advantage

⁴⁵ Wu Peng, Chinese Ambassador to Kenya H.E. Amb. Themed, "*China-Kenya cooperation headed for a brighter future*", Published on The Nation Newspaper. 2019/04/23. Available at <https://www.mfa.gov.cn/ce/ceke//eng/xw/t1656839.htm>

⁴⁶ Jing Gu, and Shen Qiu, "The Belt and Road Initiative and Africa's Sustainable Development: A Case Study of Kenya". *Institute of Development Studies Bulletin*. Vol. 50. No. 4. (2019).

⁴⁷ "Trend Economy, Annual International Trade Statistics by Country (HS02)". Reporting period: 2002 – 2020. Time series: 177 million. Source: UN Comtrade. 2021-08-09.

⁴⁸ "The Impact of Chinese Engagement on African Countries", in *Chinese Engagement in Africa: Drivers, Reactions, and Implications for U.S. Policy*, Edited by Larry Hanauer, and Lyle J. Morris. (2014), 45-54.

⁴⁹ Abokor Elmi Mohamed, "The impact of China's Development Aid on Kenya", (Saint Mary's University, Halifax, Nova Scotia. *Degree of Master of Arts in International Development Studies*, 2021), 1.

⁵⁰ Sammy Mwangi Waweru, « Who is Against Sino-African Relations? Evolving Perceptions on Chinese Engagement in Kenya », *Chinese Journal of International Review*, Vol. 2, No. 22050011 (2020): 22.

from this partnership with China".⁵¹ This seems to mean that Kenya's economic relationship with China is unbalanced but to the greater benefit of China which influences Kenyan's negative opinions towards China's economic engagement in Kenya.

According to surveys conducted among Kenyan university students, attitudes seems rather negative in relation to China as Kenya's first economic partner.⁵² Attitudes are similarly "unfavorable" with respect to the impact of Chinese projects on the economic development of the country. A study by Brendon et al explored the attitudes of Kenyan students towards China both as a beneficial economic partner for Kenya and their opinions toward Chinese projects in Kenya such as the Standard Gauge Railway (SGR)...? Figures 5 and 6 show that the younger generations of Kenyans are not in complete agreement with their leaders, who see only the benefits that China's economic commitments have had, are having and will continue to have on the country's economy.

Fig. 5. Answer results to survey question 1: Is China is a good economic partner for Kenya? Understanding African views of China: Analyses of student attitudes and elite media reportage in Kenya, by Brendon J.C., Mikiyasu N. and Dominic R.P. 2022.

Fig. 6. Answer results to survey question 2: Please tell me if you have a very favorable, somewhat favorable, somewhat unfavorable or very unfavorable opinion of Chinese projects in Kenya such as the standard gauge railway (SGR). Understanding African views of China: Analyses of student attitudes and elite media reportage in Kenya, by Brendon J.C., Mikiyasu N. and Dominic R.P. 2022.

⁵¹ Omolo M., Jairo S., & Wanja R., "Comparative Study of Kenya, US, EU and China Trade and Investment Relations". Nairobi: Institute of Economic Affairs, (2016): 29.

⁵² Brendon J. Cannon, Mikiyasu Nakayama, and Dominic R. Pkalya, "Understanding African views of China: analysis of student attitudes and elite media reportage in Kenya", Journal of Eastern African Studies, Vol. 16, No. 1, (2022): 92-114.

Such negative survey results may be explained by the fact that the younger generations fear the existence of a trap behind Chinese engagement, especially the potential debt trap that such projects may generate in the years to come.

However, at the 2018 Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC), China's President Xi Jinping argued that the goal of China-Africa relations is to make "lives better for our people" and as such, cooperation should deliver real benefits to both China and Africa.⁵³ It seems that prior to Chinese economic engagement, Kenyan development policy was ineffective in several respects especially in those economic sectors such as infrastructure where the government failed to promote development of the country's economy. Many Kenyans therefore have been impressed by how quickly the Chinese have completed major public infrastructure projects, such as roads, financed as part of the BRI.⁵⁴

According to the key facts observed in 2015 in relation of the economic development of Kenya, it was found that China enters at the right time when the Kenyan economy took its start. In 2015, the Gross National Income (GNI) of Kenya was about US\$61.8 billion while the GNI p.c. was around US\$1,340. And the GDP growth at that time was 5.6% p.a. 2011–15 despite the inflation of 6.6% p.a. 2011–15. Therefore, China and Africa have seen economic and trade cooperation expanding rapidly in scale and extent. The 10 major cooperation plans and the eight major initiatives adopted at the 2015 FOCAC Johannesburg Summit and the 2018 FOCAC Beijing Summit raised China-Africa economic and trade cooperation to a new level.⁵⁵ From 2000 to 2020, China helped African countries build more than 13,000 km of roads and railway and more than 80 large-scale power facilities, and funded over 130 medical facilities, 45 sports venues and over 170 schools.⁵⁶ That includes all the infrastructural projects in Kenya such the Mombasa Railway.

Finally, while Kenya ranks among the leaders of the post-colonial effort to industrialize in Africa, its industrial development has not been equal to its recent growth or national objectives. Manufacturing, which is a key driver of overall growth in Kenya, has declined significantly over the last three decades. As a share of GDP, manufacturing output has stagnated compared to the agriculture and services sectors, making the service sector the largest contributor to GDP.⁵⁷

BRI and Kenyas infrastructural development

The Chinese Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), also known as the New Silk Road, is an ambitious infrastructure project launched by President Xi Jinping in 2013. The BRI is a multinational, trillion-dollar development project that aims to improve connections by land and sea between China and its economic partners in Asia, Africa, the Middle East, and Europe through infrastructure plans. It has become the most prominent development initiative in history. One of the two critical components of the BRI is the 21st century Maritime Silk Road (MSR), which emphasizes Kenya.⁵⁸

⁵³ Rachel, Cooper. « The development impact of Chinese development investments in Africa », *K4D Emerging Issues Report*, Brighton UK: Institute of Development Studies University of Birmingham, (September 2019): 6.

⁵⁴ Candice Newcomb, "The impact of Chinese Investments on the Kenyan Economy", (*Master's Thesis*, Chapman University, 2020), 5.

⁵⁵ The state Council Information Office of the People's Republic of China, "China and Africa in the New Era: A Partnership of Equals", *Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China*, November, 2021.

⁵⁶ Ibidem

⁵⁷ Githaiga N., "Kenya-China Trade in Manufactured Goods: A Competitive or Complementary Relationship?", *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 9, (2021) : 96-117.

⁵⁸ Ibidem. P. 10.

Kenya, along with Ethiopia, is one of the African countries most involved in the BRI. Several memoranda of understanding and agreements across a wide range of sectors have been signed between Kenya and China in recent years.⁵⁹ These have included agreements to strengthen Chinese tourism in Kenya in 2014, to increase Kenyan agricultural exports to the Chinese market and to strengthen innovation in 2018.⁶⁰ China's relations with Kenya are a good case study in how the BRI can function in Africa and offer some answers to the thorny questions that too often arise. Indeed, the BRI has become an inextricable part of the story of "Kenya and Africa rising".⁶¹

Putting the BRI into context, China has supported Africa by constructing about 100,000 kilometers of roads, more than 10,000 km of railways, almost 100 ports and numerous hospitals and schools, as noted by State Councilor and Foreign Minister Wang Yi in March during the fifth session of the 13th National People's Congress in Beijing. By achieving these development milestones, the BRI has aligned its vision and mission with that of the African Union's Agenda 2063 and specific visions of countries, such as Kenya's Vision 2030.⁶² In Kenya, through BRI, China has supported modern infrastructure projects such as the construction of railways, roads, ports, dams, industries, airports and even digital connectivity, all of which inject vitality into the country's economic development and growth.

But why are infrastructure projects and BRI so important for Kenya's economic development? The principle reason is that Kenya more and better infrastructure to meet its development needs, whilst BRI provides the mechanism for rapidly improving its national infrastructure without any political or other conditions as would be the case with World Bank or associated international development assistance. Thus, according to the Kenyan authorities, participation in the BRI will speed up the implementation of its national development strategy⁶³ (Kenya Vision 2030).⁶⁴ Thus Kenya has become a major beneficiary of both the Maritime Silk Road and the BRI.⁶⁵ Whilst for China Kenya is considered a strategic gateway to the East African region and the focal point of its trade and economic strategy in Africa as well as safe route to facilitate the shipping of oil from Sudan.⁶⁶

For any economy to realize growth, it is imperative that a fully functional infrastructural system is in place. Indeed, according to the World Bank, in order to achieve the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the poorest

⁵⁹ Sebastien Goulard, "Obstacles to the BRI in Kenya", One Belt One Road Europe (OBOREurope), last modified July 7, 2020. <https://www.oboreurope.com/en/obstacles-bri-kenya/>

⁶⁰ Ibidem.

⁶¹ Dennis Munene, "BRI has transformed Kenya's infrastructure development", *China daily global*, (2022), Available at <https://global.chinadaily.com.cn>

⁶² Ibidem.

⁶³ Sebastien Goulard, "Obstacles to the BRI in Kenya", One Belt One Road Europe (OBOREurope), last modified July 7, 2020. <https://www.oboreurope.com/en/obstacles-bri-kenya/>

⁶⁴ The Kenya Vision 2030 aims to create "a globally competitive and prosperous country with a high quality of life by 2030". The Economic Pillar aims to achieve and sustain an average economic growth rate of 10 percent per annum until the year 2030. "Towards A Globally Competitive and Prosperous Nation", Kenya Vision 2030 Flagship Programmes and Projects Progress Report (FY 2020/2021), (August 2022), 23.

⁶⁵ Githaiga N.M., Bing W. "Belt and Road Initiative in Africa: The Impact of Standard Gauge Railway in Kenya". *China Report*; 55(3), (2019):219-240.

⁶⁶ "Opinion: FOCAC an opportunity to usher in new Sino-African cooperation", Source: CGTN, the 2018 Beijing Summit of the Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC), posted on September 6, 2018, 17:19. http://focacsummit.mfa.gov.cn/eng/zpfh_1/201809/t20180906_5862152.htm

countries must devote at least 9% of their GDP to the construction, maintenance and improvement of their national infrastructure. According to the World Bank, despite the Kenyan government significant investment in transport infrastructure with the sector recording 10% growth, Kenya requires an annual spend of \$4 billion over the next decade to close the existing infrastructure deficit. BRI is thus vital to closing that deficit. For instance, the Mombasa-Nairobi phase of the standard gauge railroad, a flagship project of Kenya's Vision 2030, cost approximately \$3.8 billion, 90% of which was financed by the Export-Import Bank of China and the rest by the Kenyan government. The 472-km-long railroad balances development and environmental protection, as 14 wildlife canals were built on the 120-km stretch of the line that runs through Kenya's Tsavo National Park.⁶⁷ Its economic impact has been immense. The railway has integrated a transportation network in East Africa, created about 46,000 jobs for local people, enhanced bilateral economic and trade development, and advanced cultural exchanges between China and Kenya. The Nairobi-Naivasha railway line, which totals 120 km and was built at a cost of \$1.48 billion, according to Kenya's Department of State for Transport and Infrastructure, will facilitate the industrialization of Africa as well as the economic prosperity of the regions along the rail line.

In addition, BRI has enabled the construction of approximately 115 km of bypass roads in Nairobi, the Nairobi Expressway (27.1 km), the Lamu-Garissa road (453 km), and 300 km of roads for informal settlements in Nairobi. These roads have been effective in reducing the daily problems faced by the Kenyan population, such as traffic congestion, and in stimulating regional economic development in East Africa by facilitating the movement of goods and services across the country. In terms of port projects, the Mombasa port berth and tank farm projects will improve traffic flow in the port, while the Kipevu oil terminal will improve the efficiency of oil transportation in Kenya.⁶⁸ Other China supported major infrastructure projects include the Thika Superhighway, Kisumu International Airport, and Jomo Kenyatta International Airport. These developments are eventually expected to enhance Kenya's economic development in the future decades. Likewise the country's new Standard Gauge Railway epitomizes what is possible through BRI. Monica Juma, Kenya's Cabinet Secretary for Foreign Affairs and International Trade, shares the vision of the BRI since it aligns perfectly with Kenya's own national growth strategy, Kenya Vision 2030, which aims to improve people's lives, on growing productivity... to be able to have a better future. As she notes, "the Chinese BRI is considered as the bridge for the future"⁶⁹ because this railway aligned and fits very well with the Kenyan government purpose of connecting the entire world. And people want to trade more and prosperity, and there won't be growth without infrastructure connection through BRI.⁷⁰

⁶⁷ Candice Newcomb, *"The impact of Chinese Investments on the Kenyan Economy"*, (MA Thesis. Chapman University, 2020), 35.

⁶⁸ Dennis Munene, "BRI has transformed Kenya's infrastructure development", *China daily global*, (2022), Available at <https://global.chinadaily.com.cn>.

⁶⁹ Monica Juma, "Kenya: A BRI success story", Interview of the Cabinet secretary, Ministry of Foreign Affairs and International Trade. Kenya. CGTN: World insight. 2019.

⁷⁰ Monica Juma, "Kenya: A BRI success story", Interview of the Cabinet secretary, Ministry of Foreign Affairs and International Trade. Kenya. CGTN: World insight. 2019.

Projects	USD
Jomo Kenyatta International Airport	115 million
Thika Super Highway	320 million
LAPPSET Highway	220 million
SGR	3,6 billion
Geothermal project at Olkari	400 million
Kenya Power Distribution System Modernization Project in Malindi	185 million
Outer Ring Road	108 million
Nairobi Mombasa Super Highway	320 million

Table 1. Chinese contribution to Kenyan infrastructural development. Adapted data from "Effect on Kenya's bilateral relations with China on economic growth of Kenya (2000-2015)", by S. Wanjiku, 2018, p.2.

In last two decades, China has invested extensively in enhancing Kenya's national infrastructure (See Table 1) through development projects in sectors from transport, energy, education, to health, and digital connectivity which have significantly improved the welfare of the population. Chinese investment has shown positive impacts in infrastructure and government projects which is really important for Kenya's economic development since in the past, government construction projects were characterized by inefficiency taking longer than expected due to shoddy work, corruption and procrastination. Furthermore forging economic relations with China makes it possible for states like Kenya to reduce their dependence on Western countries. A distinction is sometimes made between the "Beijing Consensus" and the "Washington Consensus", with many Africans seeking to establish partnerships with China on less restrictive terms than those imposed by European and American partners or by international organizations. However, such freedom comes with risks since China agrees to finance infrastructure projects which other partners refuse because they do not consider them viable.

Conclusion and Findings

The China-Africa economic relationship which was formalized in the year 2000 has become productive for both partners. China is today an essential trade partner of Africa, contributing to the development of African countries. A majority of Kenyans (more than 60%) approve of Chinese economic engagement in the country citing China's role in infrastructural development and investment in business as the main reason. Furthermore, more than 75% of Kenyans perceive China to have a positive influence on the country's development aspirations, while 67% consider beneficial Chinese development assistance to the country⁷¹. But increased Chinese economic engagement has attracted mixed and varied reactions of approval and disapproval in a number of host countries. ⁷² For some, despite the very real gains, there are areas where the relationship between China and Africa could and should be improved.⁷³

Over past decade, many African nations have accumulated higher debt-burdens including Kenya. Each country profile is unique whilst significant debt accumulated before China became a major lender. Debt relief for African countries is becoming an important topic on the international agenda. Being a large creditor, China will have a

⁷¹ Sammy Mwangi Waweru, « Who is Against Sino-African Relations? Evolving Perceptions on Chinese Engagement in Kenya », *Chinese Journal of International Review* Vol. 2, No. 22050011. (2020): 12.

⁷² Ibidem.

⁷³ Irene Yuan Sun, Jayaram Kartik, and Kassiri Omid, « Dance of the Lions and the Dragons: How are Africa and China engaging, and how will the partnership evolve? », *McKinsey & Company*, (June 2017).

significant role in the process. So by loans, China played a big role in Africa's economic development, and especially in Kenyan economic development.

As this study shows China, through BRI and development assistance, has invested hugely to close Kenya's infrastructure deficit. Kenya's Vision 2030 development strategy aims to create "a globally competitive and prosperous country with a high quality of life by 2030⁷⁴ whilst its Economic Pillar aims to achieve and sustain an average economic growth rate of 10 percent per annum until the year 2030.⁷⁵ But to sustain this growth, Kenya requires modern infrastructure to meet its development needs for as advocates of infrastructural development theory note such investment is an essential driving force to achieve rapid and sustained economic growth because infrastructure is the prerequisite for the development of any economy. Moreover, to sustain its strategic advantage as an African hub Kenya must continue to improve its infrastructure (transport, power and digital) through both public and private investments in order to lead the integration of regional markets.⁷⁶ BRI and Chinese development assistance is a vital contribution to achieving Kenya's Vision 2030 development strategy. Indeed, major infrastructure investment projects mostly financed by China, such as the SGR, are major factors driving Kenya's economic development. For such infrastructures are long-term investments creating economic opportunities boosting the national economy of Kenya at first and then those neighboring countries and can serve as a development model for a better strategy for the future prospects of all the countries in that region.

To conclude China's increasing economic engagement in Kenya over the past two decades has contributed significantly to the country's economic development. Moreover increased economic engagement between China and Kenya has influenced the economic development strategy of the Kenyan government in so far as it has become more closely aligned with China's statist development model which prioritizes infrastructural investment.

However, as a final observation, there is still more to do for China to become indispensable to Africa, more precisely to Kenya's economic development; for instance, the Chinese engagement in Africa through infrastructural investment which has increased recently since 2000.

Whilst this study may serve as an inspiration for other African states on the importance of infrastructure for national economic development governments have an important *responsibility to protect citizens from any potential risks of Chinese or other foreign investments, most*, especially for megaprojects such as the SGR in Kenya. On the other hand, Kenya's experience may also serve as a policy lesson for those states still hesitant to follow the Chinese economic development model in order to ensure rapid economic growth by integrating into large projects such as the BRI.

⁷⁴ "Towards A Globally Competitive and Prosperous Nation", Kenya Vision 2030 Flagship Programmes and Projects Progress Report (FY 2020/2021), (August 2022), 23.

⁷⁵ Ibidem

⁷⁶ World Bank. "The World Bank in Kenya: The World Bank's work in Kenya supports the government's Vision 2030 development strategy, which aims to accelerate sustainable growth, reduce inequality, and manage resource scarcity". *World Bank report* in March 2021. Available at <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/kenya/overview#1> p7

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